

Bernard Flaman

“Airport as city square”: Toronto, Edmonton and Winnipeg Airports, 1964

Architects

Toronto Airport: John B. Parkin and Associates

Winnipeg Airport: Green Blankstein and Russel Architects

Edmonton Airport: Rensa and Minsos Architects

Introduction

Fig. 1 – Edmonton Concourse

The title of this presentation is borrowed from Deyan Sudjec’s 1992 book “The 100 Mile City”. The chapter, “Airport as City Square” traces the evolution of the modern airport and presents a thesis where the airport is described as a traditional city in programmatic terms that includes public spaces, workplaces and transportation. However, these traditional civic elements are rendered in an urban form that has never existed before.

The following, documents a series of very powerful civic spaces created within three Canadian Airports, Toronto, Winnipeg and Edmonton. It explores the political and formal underpinnings of these projects and the relationship between public art and the public space in which it is housed. The Winnipeg airport is discussed as an example of critical regionalism that developed within the tenants of modernism.

Political Agenda

Between 1959 and 1968, the Canadian government, through the Department of Transportation completed seven major new airport terminals. A set of three in Toronto, Winnipeg and Edmonton, were completed in early 1964, and became the first terminals in Canada to be designed for jet passenger aircraft. The technical objectives for the so-called “jetports” were not yet completely formulated and the design process exhibited a certain level of exploration and experimentation with basic passenger flows. The result was three different approaches that shared the common programmatic elements of ticket concourse, public lounge, VIP lounge, arrivals area, restaurant and lunch counter.

Fig. 2 – Toronto Front

Toronto Airport was the largest and most daring. Originally conceived as the first of several “Aeroquays”, it was based on a circular plan form to minimize walking distances with an integral multi-story parking garage. Passengers arrived by a roadway that dipped below the aircraft ramp, similar to Heathrow, and emerged in front of the concourse in the centre of the building. From there it was a short walk to the hold rooms that ringed the concourse and lounges. The materiality of the complex was dominated by an exposed concrete structure infilled with glass.

The Edmonton terminal, with separate departure and arrival levels and roadways, displays what has become one of the most common terminal forms. The building, monumental in form with a taut glass skin, had a conventional steel domino frame.

The Winnipeg airport was deemed too small by the department of transport for an areoquay scheme or a two level roadway, so the designers compensated with an elegant, clear span departures and arrivals building. It is evident from these examples that the form of the modern airport terminal was in the process of being invented and its evolution progressed significantly during the early days of jet passenger travel.

One objective over which there seemed to be no confusion and would guide the design of each building was that the terminals would convey a thoroughly modern and up to date national image that would serve as an introduction to Canada and its culture to the foreign traveler. It would also represent a unifying force to the citizens of a large nation composed of several different linguistic, cultural and topographic regions.

To this end, the Department of Transport allocated ½ of one percent of the project budget for artwork, commissioned the top modernist architects in each city and placed special emphasis on the furniture that would complete the vision of a government sponsored public space of national importance.

The product, as the photographic documentation makes clear, would be a series of sleek, beautifully designed buildings that housed 20 pieces of painting and sculpture commissioned with the guidance of the National Gallery, and the latest in Canadian and Internationally designed furniture. These buildings formed part of an air transportation system that would connect the country and eclipse the railroad as a means of passenger travel. Symbolically, they projected a powerful image of Canada as a modern, unified nation.

The impetus for this series of exemplary buildings had its roots in a conscious effort of social and cultural engineering on the part of the federal government.

The writing of artist Ken Lum, has divided post Second World War cultural production into two principal stages. The Massey-Levesque commission of 1949, a massive two-year inquiry that set cultural policy for the next twenty years and was instrumental in establishing the National Library, the National Film Board and The Canada Council for the Arts, marked the first stage. The Canadian Multicultural Act of 1971 represented the beginning of the second stage.

Lum states that the Massey-Levesque commission

"... was in fact a document of the intellectual anxieties of Canada's ruling Anglophone elite worried about the ascending signs of regional discontent to which they believed themselves historically designated to resolve."

He goes on to say,

"The task of the commission as it defined it was a difficult one: how to construct an identity for a nation that was comprised of isolated regions of diverse histories and to which the threat of American influences was always present". (Lum, 1999: pp. 76-83)

The Toronto, Winnipeg and Edmonton Airports serve as a visual example of the post-war directives of the Canadian Government toward a unified identity and culture.

Formal Agenda

The ambitions of the Massey-Levesque commission in Canada coincided with the rise of a variation of Modernism that argued in favour of a "highly charged iconographic reading of architecture". Canadian architect and theorist, George Baird describes this movement in his 1995 book "The Space of Appearance". He discusses Colin Rowe's 1947 essay, "The Mathematics of the Ideal Villa" and Rowe's mentor, Rudolf Wittkower's 1949 publication of "Architectural Principles in the Age of Humanism". Baird states:

"Indeed, Rowe's and Wittkower's publications can be seen in retrospect as a starting point of the phenomenon that became known both in Europe and North America, as neo-Palladianism. With the advent of the new interest in symmetry, centrality, and elementary volume, which was increasingly evident in the American work of Mies van der Rohe from that period, neo-Palladianism quickly became linked with a putative neo-classicism. As Rowe put it:

"Neo-Palladianism ...has inherited – particularly from Mies- a sense of propriety.

It has adopted particularly from him an ordinance of the building envelope.

It has been led by him to accept as sufficient the statement of elementary volume.

Its preferred textures, its taste for big scale and immaculate finish are largely

Miesian, while it has enjoyed the same sanction for its symmetrical solutions." (Baird, 1995: page 149)

When Bernard Brown, one of the original designers of the Winnipeg airport along with David Thordarson of the office of Green Blankstein and Russell, was asked where the inspiration for the design concept came from, his answer was one word, "Mies". (Brown, 2000: interview)

This monumental, symmetrical, minimalist form of modernism would be used to create a nationalist Canadian identity in the Jet Age. To quote Deyan Sudjic:

"... early airports, represented an era in which flying was a gentlemanly recreation... What followed them was the baroque phase of airport building, characterized by the outward show of luxury... This was the modern world in its *Dolce Vita* incarnation: Cuban heels, Dacron, midnight-blue suits, and silver metal aircraft waiting to whisk the masters of the universe away." (Sudjic, 1992: page 153)

The photographs depict an amazing consistency of approach. The details varied, but it is obvious that there was a guiding force behind the creation of these civic spaces. Department of Transport architect, Stanley White, was instrumental in coordinating the overall image. Educated at the University of Toronto, he served as the secretary of the fine art committee and went on to work on Expo 67 immediately after the airport terminal projects. Quoted in a popular magazine of the day:

"There was no catering to popular taste ... We were trying to achieve for Canada the most sophisticated image we possibly could." There was no regional favouritism. He felt that it would be a service to Canadian culture to expose a Vancouver artist in Edmonton, Montreal artists in Toronto, Toronto artists in Winnipeg." (Lowe, 1964: pp. 144-5)

Nationalism vs. Regionalism

The "popular taste" referred to was perhaps linked with a Canadian self-image of a country dominated by nature as depicted by the Group of Seven and Emily Carr. The sophisticated image promoted by White on behalf of the Federal Government created a dramatic and urbane image of nature stripped down and abstracted into colour and form.

Evan H. Turner, the director of the Montreal Museum of Art, in his 1964 review of the airport art project alluded to the tensions that had been, to this point simmering under the surface, but are still discernable today upon reading the minutes of the art committee meetings. The battle lines seemed clearly drawn between those who promoted a national or international perspective and those who preferred to project a regionalist image.

Turner's review of the project states that:

"... the Department of Transport's selection has been exemplary for selecting outstanding artists and not sacrificing standards to the undue pressures of regionalism that might have been feared." (Turner, 1964: page 131)

Here, Bernard Brown recollects discussions concerning the selection of two sculptures by artists Richard Williams and Jack Harman that were considered too regional and too provincial. The report prepared by his firm in 1963 gives a clue as to where the regional pressures that Turner feared stemmed from:

"The Winnipeg International terminal is primarily serving connecting flight passengers, and as such an art program should be concerned with establishing a cultural image of the prairies." (Fine Art Program report, 1964)

In the midst of this nationalistic atmosphere, the Winnipeg terminal moved through many schemes. The critique of each scheme is unknown today, but studying the drawings seems to point to several concerns that focus on image, passenger flow and budget. The initial designs display an overtly Frank Lloyd Wright character, in keeping with a self-image of Winnipeg as Chicago of the north. By scheme 7, the Miesian Neo-Palladianism that would give the Winnipeg terminal a stylistic affinity with Edmonton and Toronto is fully developed. In this scheme, we see a hotel and carpark that define a central axis and a terminal that spreads across the flat open landscape with separate arrivals and departures buildings on one level and large open courtyards. If we take Kenneth Frampton's definition of critical regionalism as a dialogue between tectonics and topography, (Frampton, 1988: pp. 4-7) this scheme must be considered to be strongly regionalist in the way it captures and orders the expansive landscape.

As the design moved through subsequent iterations, ending finally with scheme 13r, the regional essence and modernist style remain as the terminal becomes consolidated and more compact responding to the realities of the budget. The courtyards are still evident, but are radically reduced in size; the administration building has been separated from the terminal and takes the axial position of the deleted hotel and carpark.

The terminal was finally designed with a single level roadway, with the ability to expand to separate departures and arrivals levels. A second level mezzanine planned as a future ticketing concourse overlooked the main level, where ticket counters filled the centre portion, flanked by luggage carousels at either end.

This almost accidental space, vast and awaiting its function, became a link with topography of the Winnipeg area. Floating above the main level, it was as expansive and filled with light, as the prairie itself and beautifully framed by the previously discussed structuralist murals that engage the space, both literally and with colour.

Fig.3 – Winnipeg Mezzanine

A third mural by Alfred Pelan, combined his surrealist style with a startling colour scheme. Entitled, "The Prairie", it formed the entrance from the mezzanine to the dining area.

During a 1996 lecture, George Baird spoke of "visibility, overlook, spaciality, focality, inclusiveness and otherness" as necessary elements of a fully constituted public realm. The embodiment of these elements within the Winnipeg airport transcended nationalistic goals to create a civic space of unparalleled power; a regionalist expression within the tenants of modernism.

Conclusion

The completed spaces caused a sensation and received mixed reviews from the public. The artworks, in particular became a target of criticism related to their cost and abstract meaning. With \$250,000 spent on abstract art, the program was ridiculed and lampooned.

Modernistic blobs, paint smears, welder's experiments and carpenter's leftovers are some of the terms that appeared in the popular press. The few that survive in their original locations are the last pieces of the airport interiors that have been radically changed over the past 35 years.

Canada is in the midst of another airport building boom caused by the shift from government to private ownership. The building shells are modern and there is a concerted effort to evoke a regional flavour, mainly through the design of retail areas that simulate parts of the city or region where the airport is located. The design of these areas has become a prime concern of airport authorities as most modern airports derive a substantial portion of their income from retail sales.

Now crowded, as air travel has become commonplace, the airport public realm has merged with the shopping mall and the amusement park. The "airport as City Square" now derives its excitement and vibrancy from the sheer number of people that move through it rather than from the power of the space itself.

James Twitchell, in his book *Lead Us Into Temptation* writes:

"High culture has pretty much disappeared, desperately needing such infusions of life-preserving monies from taxpayer-supported endowments and tax-free foundations to keep it from gasping away. One might wonder if there's anything more to American life than shopping." (Stackhouse, 1999:A15)

This trend is highly evident in the current state of the Winnipeg airport, where two murals, of the three that are still intact, are almost obliterated by advertising and retail kiosks. A regionalist connection is attempted, with palpable irony, in the design of the national brand shops by copying details from the restored warehouse district in downtown Winnipeg.

The progression from the cool, minimalist "high culture" atmosphere of the original spaces to the revenue driven themed retail of the current interiors was encapsulated last fall in the second part of the "American Century" exhibition at the Whitney Museum in New York.

The exhibition began with paintings by Jackson Pollock and ended with advertisements for "The Gap". It is perhaps a question of quality. Perhaps "khakis rock, khakis groove and khakis swing", express the spirit of our time, especially when displayed on Sony plasma screen monitors, as well and with as much controversy as Pollock's abstract expressionist drip paintings of the early 1950's.

In Winnipeg, however, the current retail design fails to respond to the essence of the mezzanine space that so brilliantly evoked the atmosphere of the Canadian prairie and has replaced it with a literal regionalism that collapses into confusion and kitsch.

The airport as a building type is perhaps ill suited to historic preservation as it embodies the rapid pace of technological and social change in the last half of the twentieth century. These buildings survive best in the form of photographic documentation that depicts a moment in this fast paced and disposable time period. The photographs presented here serve as a record of the collective cultural aspirations of a nation and a visual representation of a country clambering for a place on the world stage in the post-war era. It was a world accustomed to seeing the landscape of Canada represented through the eyes of the Group of Seven. The artworks and the architecture of the Toronto, Winnipeg and Edmonton airports combined to created spaces that were inspired by the natural landscape of Canada, but brilliantly reinterpreted it in the modernist idiom.

These spaces offered a new look that challenged the traditional representation of Canada, depicting

a level of modernity that the public was not yet quite ready for.

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KEYWORDS

Regionalism, Public art, Public space, Canadian airports, Modernism

Bernard Flaman. Born in 1959, Bernard Flaman was raised on a farm in Saskatchewan, Canada. He studied Art History at the University of Saskatchewan, receiving a Bachelor of Arts degree in 1981 and studied architecture at the University of Toronto, receiving a Bachelor of Architecture degree in 1987. He spent time as a visiting student with the University of Toronto in Paris France and at the Southern California Institute of Architecture in Los Angeles, California. Bernard has worked in the USA, Germany and Canada. Some of the projects he has been involved with include a competition for the National Theatre in Tokyo Japan with the office of Eric Owen Moss and a wood research facility for the University of British Columbia. He has acted as project architect for the new airport terminal in Moncton, New Brunswick, the design of retail renovations for the San Antonio Airport and a health clinic for the aboriginal community of Bella Bella in northern British Columbia. He became interested in the history of modernist architecture at Canadian airports while part of the design team working on the expansion of the Edmonton Airport. Bernard is currently engaged in private practise in Saskatoon, Canada.

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